

*Research Lifecycle Management technologies for
Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC*

Deliverable D7.1

Report on Earth Science multidisciplinary case study on 2020 lockdown: requirements, testing, demonstration and population

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List of authors, contributors and reviewers

Name	Role	Organization
Federica Foglini	Author	CNR
Valentina Grande	Author	CNR
Giorgio Castellan	Contributor	CNR
Katrin Schroeder	Contributor	CNR
Fantina Madricardo	Contributor	CNR
Antonio Petrizzo	Contributor	CNR
Federico Falcini	Contributor	CNR
Simona Aracri	Contributor	CNR
Malek Belgacem	Contributor	CNR
Anne Fouilloux	Contributor	UiO
Jean laquinta	Contributor	UiO
Elisa Trasatti	Contributor	INGV

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Glossary

Acronym	Explanation
ADAM	Advanced geospatial Data Management
ADS	Atmosphere Data Store
API	Application Programming Interface
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
CC	Creative Common
CEO	Committee on Earth Observation Satellites
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
CS	Scenario
CWL	Common Workflow Language
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DS	Dataset
EEA	European Environment Agency
EGI	European Grid Infrastructure
EO	Earth Observation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPOS	Portal and the European Catalogue of Volcanoes
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GEO	Group on Earth Observation
GES	Good Environmental Status
GS	Grand Challenge
GSNL	Geohazard Supersites and Natural Laboratories
INES	Earth System modelling
INGV	Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia
ISMAR	Istituto di Scienze Marine
MEEO	Meteorological and Environmental Earth Observation

MetOs	Meteorology and Oceanography
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NCEI	National Centers for Environmental Information
NILU	Norwegian Institute for Air Research
NIRD	Norwegian Infrastructure for Research Data Archive
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NRT	Near Real Time
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
RELIANCE	Research Lifecycle Management technologies for Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC
RI	Research Infrastructure
RO	Research Object
SPL	Sound Pressure Level
tbd	to be defined
TO	Tool
UiO	Universitetet i Oslo
UPM	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VRC	Virtual Research Communities
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WAV	Waveform Audio File Format
WoP	Web of Science
WP	Work package
WPL	Work Package Leaders
WPS	Web Processing Service

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Executive Summary

The RELIANCE Project (Research Lifecycle Management for Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC) aims to realize the vision of FAIR research in EOSC by adopting a holistic research management approach based on three key and complementary technologies: i) Research objects (RO) as the overarching mechanism to manage scientific research activities, which relies upon ROHub platform as the reference service; ii) data cubes as the mechanisms enabling an efficient and scalable Earth Observation (EO) data access and discovery, which relies upon the Advanced geospatial Data Management (ADAM) platform as the reference service; iii) text mining and semantic enrichment services allowing to extract machine-readable metadata from RO resources, enabling researchers to discover scientific information at scale and to structure their own research.

In this framework, the overall purpose of WP7 is to demonstrate the efficacy of the RELIANCE services within the EOSC context through real-life multidisciplinary user case studies provided by different scientific communities.

The specific objectives of this work package are the following:

- build a shared multidisciplinary research framework on the 2020 lockdown consequences using Earth Science data, by means of a Research Object-based approach;
- expand the 2020 lockdown Earth Science case studies including the societal/economical domain demonstrating the RELIANCE capacity to sustain heterogeneous communities;
- ensure the wide adoption of the RELIANCE services by developing multidisciplinary use cases for the Earth Science communities;
- validate the RELIANCE services in the EOSC context.

This deliverable **T7.1** aims at reporting the Multidisciplinary case study on 2020 Lockdown consequences on the environment. The Scientific communities built a shared multidisciplinary research framework using Earth Science data acquired during the 2020 lockdown which generated a fast, drastic and intense reduction of the anthropic pressure on the environment. The team studied **the effects of anthropic pressure reduction under the marine and atmospheric perspective**. It collected and shared information on environmental variables, sampling strategies, spatial and temporal reduction, sampling methodologies and model experiments linked to changes detected across the pre-pandemic and post-pandemic phases. The joint research activities carried out by means of a Research Object-based approach led to the creation of an Earth Science Lockdown Research Object Inventory containing valuable multidisciplinary research information publicly available.

1. Introduction

1.1. Scope

This document briefly describes the scientific communities involved in the multidisciplinary case study on 2020 lockdown and the scientific context they operate. It presents a catalog of several scenarios implemented by the communities linked to the lockdown 2020 including a brief description, the type of actions needed, and the resources involved. Each resource is described in detail including the **type, the associated documentation, a short description and a link**, if possible.

The document provides the requirements to the RELIANCE technical partners for each of the scenarios, and describes the results of the test of the RELIANCE services and the RO population.

1.2. Audience

This deliverable is intended for internal use by the RELIANCE Consortium and open to public.

1.3. Structure

The rest of the document is structured as follows:

- Section 2 describes shortly the 3 RELIANCE scientific communities: the **Sea Monitoring** and **Atmospheric and Climate modelling** communities, working specifically on the multidisciplinary case study on the 2020 lockdown and the **Geohazard Supersites and Natural Laboratories community** contributing to the definition of the technical requirements for the RELIANCE Services (see section 4)
- Section 3 describes the scientific context for the multidisciplinary case studies on the 2020 lockdown. This section also presents the use case scenarios and the Research Objects implemented so far;
- Section 4 presents the requirements for the RELIANCE services and other EOSC services needed to fully satisfy the scientific scenarios. For each requirement we specify if this is mandatory or desirable, the source, and the status. These requirements will be updated during the project if an evolution of the scenarios occurs;
- Section 5 shows the Research Objects implemented for the scenarios related to COVID19 lockdown. In particular, this section reports all the tools tested and used to produce and populate the ROs.

2. Scientific communities

2.1. The Sea Monitoring Virtual Research Community

The Sea Monitoring VRC involves marine scientists, in particular ecologists, biologists, geologists, geophysicists, geochemists, oceanographers, paleoceanographers and Earth observation experts studying the marine habitats, the present and past dynamics of the ocean and the interface between ocean and atmosphere, with a particular focus on the Mediterranean and the polar regions, focusing on the following themes:

- the evolution of oceans and their continental margins, studying submarine volcanoes, faults and slides and their potential impacts onshore. The influence of climate change on oceanic circulation, seawater chemistry, bio geochemical cycles, marine ecosystems and marine productivity;
- submarine habitats and ecology, and the increasing pollution of coastal and deep-sea environments;
- natural and anthropogenic factors impacting economically and socially on coastal systems from pre- history to the industrial epoch.

2.2. The Atmospheric and Climate modelling community

The Atmospheric and Climate modelling community involves scientists working on the development of numerical meteorological, ocean and climate models as well as collecting and analyzing related data. The Norwegian Infrastructure for Earth System modelling (INES) provides the foundation for research of strategic relevance for Norwegian climate science and a basis for international cooperation efforts aimed at better understanding future climate change and associated mitigation needs. The Section for Meteorology and Oceanography (MetOs) of the University of Oslo will represent this community in the RELIANCE project and will foster the adoption of RELIANCE services. This is *per se* a multidisciplinary group involved in a broad range of activities from modelling wave-oil interaction to predicting the future climate and its economic impacts. Researchers and professors supervise students from Bachelor to postdoctoral levels.

2.3. The Geohazard Supersites and Natural Laboratories (geo-gsnl.org) community

The Geohazard Supersites and Natural Laboratories (GEO-GSNL geo-gsnl.org) community is a global initiative part of the Group on Earth Observation (GEO), aiming at improving scientific knowledge of volcanic and seismic supersites to support disaster risk reduction. Over each supersite or natural laboratory (characterized by high volcanic and seismic hazard) an international partnership collaborates to assess the related hazards based on satellite imagery provided at no cost by CEOS, and with other geophysical data provided by the local monitoring institutions. The general goal of the GSNL initiative is pursued by promoting the full adoption of the Open Science principles and practices, through a constant sharing of data, knowledge, and capacities within the local and global scientific communities. The global community focuses on most of the geohazards related to pre-eruptive and eruptive phases of the volcanic activity, and on the entire seismic cycle (long-term interseismic, coseismic and post-seismic phases). In particular, the focus for volcanic areas is on:

- volcano deformations
- seismic activity related to volcanoes
- gas emissions
- lava mapping
- ash and SO₂ emissions

3. Multidisciplinary case studies on 2020 lockdown

This use case aims to quantify the de-impact of the lockdown on the atmospheric and marine coastal environment, highlighting the role of open data and availability of pre-pandemic, pandemic, and post-pandemic data. The main objectives of this case study is to: 1) assess the evolution of the anthropogenic impact on the atmospheric and marine-coastal systems following the lockdown in Europe and in Mediterranean areas with high urban and/or industrial density; 2) quantify in a synoptic way, the air quality and good environmental status (GES) of the sea (MSFD) at the end of the lockdown phase, by directly applying open data approach followed by further elaborations; 3) integrate measures whenever available from the observation sites within the scientific networks involved, adding (i) bespoke measures in hotspots subject to maximum change, (ii) qualitative evidence from observations of citizens according to the local ecological knowledge approach; 4) build a shared vision among different actors by engaging citizens of the mapped areas and relevant stakeholders, e.g. fishermen and/or health services, in data acquisition, interpretation and validation, as well as in the discussion on the project results and its perspectives.

Since the beginning of March 2020 many European (and non-European) countries went into an unprecedented lockdown. Most of the economic and industrial activities have been interrupted, citizens were invited to stay at home, transport (individual, collective and freight) stalled, tourism was virtually absent everywhere, and cruise ships stopped. After almost 2 months, some countries tried to start to re-open specific sectors of social and economic lives, industry and agriculture began to recover in some areas, tourism (especially international and mass-tourism) however remained at very low levels for many months. While on the one hand this has been a catastrophic situation from a health, economical, psychological and social point of view, on the other hand we witnessed an exceptional “experiment” of a fast, drastic and intense reduction of the anthropogenic pressure on the environment, especially in regions that are characterized by big urban and industrial agglomerates as well as mass tourism.

This case study seeks to understand and quantify the (de-)impact of the lockdown on the marine coastal and atmospheric environments by networking with other organizations in Europe focusing on

initiatives devoted to this assessment. The “big questions” these initiatives would address are for instance: what are the actual effects on the reduction of the anthropogenic input in terms of water quality of the coastal environment? What was the impact on atmospheric emissions (and thereby climate) of this period with reduced activities in the industry (factories slow-down, raw material extraction stopped, etc.), trade (no more sea/air/land shipping), agriculture (delays in irrigation, harvesting), mobility (drastic decrease in the use of individual/collective transport means), etc. Can we learn something through this “experiment” about how to better reduce our impact on the environment? Can we collect useful information for a future sustainable and more efficient management of our surroundings once the lockdown has finished?

3.1. Scenario 1 “Bibliography analysis on lockdown related papers within Earth science”

Since the beginning of March 2020 many European (and non-European) countries went into an unprecedented lockdown. As a consequence a large number of papers trying to analyze the effects of the anthropause on the marine environment has been published around the world. The aim of this scenario is to collect and analyze the scientific papers produced in the last year about marine science. This information will be the basis for the other scenarios in this section.

The following table summarizes the actions carried out during the scenario:

Action ID	Action description	Resources
1	Valentina collects all the scientific papers about lockdown in marine sciences using Web of Science	DS1-GC0-SC1
2	Valentina creates a bibliographic RO collecting the references to the scientific papers (DS1-GC0-SC1)	RO1-GC0-SC1
2	Federica automatically creates n bibliographic ROs (one for each paper)	RO2-GC0-SC1
3	Federica would like to analyze the database and check which are concepts, domains, frequent expressions and places	-
4	Federica updates RO1-GC0-SC1, by linking as internal resources all the Bibliographic RO produced (RO2-GC0-SC1) and loading the analysis results	-
5	Katrin uses these results in the scenario 3 to be compared with the results coming from questionnaires	-

The following tables describe the resources re-used or produced during the scenario:

Resource ID	DS1-GC0-SC1	Name	List of scientific papers
Format	excel file (.xls)	Size	ca. 300 KB
Source	The list of papers comes from the Web of Science (WoS; previously known as Web of Knowledge), a website that provides subscription-based access to multiple databases that provide comprehensive citation data for many different academic disciplines		
Type	Produced		
License	CC-BY		
Description	Collection of scientific papers about lockdown in marine sciences		

Resource ID	RO1-GC0-SC1	Name	Earth Sciences papers about COVID19 lockdown
Format	Bibliographic RO	Size	ca. 300 KB
Source	https://w3id.org/ro-id/7f025f6e-9835-4af8-aa48-0152474eda37		
Type	Produced		
License	CC-BY		
Description	Bibliographic RO integrating all the collected scientific papers		

Resource ID	RO2-GC0-SC1	Name	n/a
Format	Bibliographic ROs	Size	n/a
Source	n/a		
Type	Produced		
License	CC-BY		
Description	Set of Bibliographic ROs. Each paper has a Ro with a short description and content based annotations.		

3.2. Scenario 2 “Marine Monitoring during the Anthropause”

This scenario collects information on efforts to monitor the reduction of human impact on Mediterranean marine ecosystems due to the lockdowns that took place in different countries during 2020-2021 ("Anthropause").

The following table summarizes the actions carried out during the scenario:

Action ID	Action description	Resources
1	Katrin and Simona prepare a questionnaire to get information about the marine monitoring during the anthropause	DS1-GC0-SC2
2	Katrin and Simona create a basic RO to share the first version of the questionnaire with colleagues	RO1-GC0-SC2
3	Colleagues contribute to questionnaire and upload the new version in the shared RO	
4	Katrin and Simona distribute the questionnaires, they collect the results and put them on the shared RO	
5	Simona analyses the filled questionnaires with text mining tools, visualizes the results through the dashboard and put them in the shared RO	
6	Katrin uses the results for her paper and also includes the DOI of the RO in the paper	

The following tables describe the resources re-used or produced during the scenario:

Resource ID	DS1-GC0-SC2	Name	Questionnaire
Format	URL	Size	62 KB
Source	The questionnaire is produced during the scenario starting from expert opinions and it is available at the link: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSe9yaL-IV4bLW41sc482YxxV-TKYP6WtLK7iTVehgWORTTqrg/viewform?usp=sf_link		

Type	Produced
License	CC-BY
Description	The questionnaire aims at understanding and quantifying the (de-)impact of the lockdown on the marine coastal and atmospheric environments networking with other organizations in Europe focusing on initiatives devoted to this assessment

Resource ID	RO1-GC0-SC2	Name	Marine Monitoring during the Anthro pause
Format	Basic RO	Size	40 MB
Source	https://w3id.org/ro-id/49f52ad4-bf2c-4f50-9242-a26962d5a7a2		
Type	Produced		
License	CC-BY		
Description	This RO collects information on efforts to monitor the reduction of human impact on mediterranean marine ecosystems due to the lockdowns that took place in different countries during 2020-2021 ("Anthro pause")		

3.3. Scenario 3 "Impact of the Covid-19 Lockdown on Air quality"

In this scenario, the impact of the lockdown and overall reduction of human activities on the air quality over different areas in Europe during 2019-2020-2021 period is studied. To get an accurate and consistent coverage of anthropogenic emissions such as NO₂, PM_{2.5}, O₃, data from Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service will be used as a primary source of information but local measurements (whenever available) could complement this study.

The following table summarizes the actions carried out during the scenario:

Action ID	Action description	Resources
1	Lasse collects in a new RO all relevant bibliography, press releases, etc. on the impact of lockdown and the reduction of human activities on air quality. Emphasis can be put on large cities, industrial areas, land and maritime transport routes. This also takes into account information about areas where ferries stayed at the dock and local population "complained" about an increase in the air pollution	RO1-GC0-SC3
2	Lasse explores Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring analysis from the ADAM platform to select areas of studies. Lasse selects NO ₂ , PM _{2.5} and O ₃ variables for a geographical area covering Europe and 3 different time periods: March-June 2019, March-June 2020 and March-June 2021 to provide information about the pre-lockdown, actual lockdown and post-lockdown, respectively. When/where necessary the available data will be re-gridded to ensure continuity of the analysis over the entire period of interest. Lasse creates a new RO and adds a Jupyter Notebook to extract and pre-process the relevant data. The result of this process is stored and shared as geoTIFF (data extracted from Data Cube) and netCDF files (1 per variable) in a Galaxy history of Galaxy Europe.	DS1-GC0-SC3 RO2-GC0-SC3
3	Lasse uses the same Jupyter Notebook to derive statistical quantities, create time series for selected locations and for the three time periods (before, during and after lockdown/reduction of human activities) and for each pollutant	RO2-GC0-SC3
4	To complement his previous analysis, Lasse uses Galaxy Tools and creates a Galaxy Workflow to compute air quality statistics for some	RO3-GC0-SC3

	geographical areas, periods and chemical species. Here the focus is on small geographical areas (and not single locations) for instance Marseille (West and North areas) and/or Venice. The goal is to understand the variability of air quality in some cities where citizens have reported significant changes during the lockdown and check if this is effectively observed with Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring data	
5	Lasse extracts his workflow from Galaxy history, register it in WorkflowHub with a DOI and add it to his RO	RO3-GC0-SC3
6	Lasse compares with local measurements if available and create a new RO with the resulting analysis	RO4-GC0-SC3
7	Lasse runs a so-called trajectory model (i.e., backwards in time) to find the source of pollution. He has identified for this purpose potential tools such as FLEXPART or HYSPLIT or LAGRANTO	RO5-GC0-SC3
8	Using all his results, Lasse publishes his final report with associated metadata in rohub	RO6-GC0-SC33

The following tables describe the resources re-used or produced during the scenario:

Resource ID	DS1-GC0-SC3	Name	CAMS European air quality forecasts
Format	geoTIFF from ADAM	Size	470GB
Source	<p>Data is originally from the CAMS Atmosphere Data Store (ADS) and has been made available via the ADAM platform for easy integration into Research Objects. All the available variables e.g. 'ammonia', 'carbon monoxide', '<u>nitrogen dioxide</u>', 'nitrogen monoxide', 'non methane vocs', 'ozone', 'particulate matter 10um (PM10)', '<u>particulate matter 2.5um (PM2.5)</u>', 'peroxyacyl nitrates', 'residential elementary carbon', 'secondary inorganic aerosol', 'sulfur dioxide', 'total elementary carbon', '<u>ozone</u>' are available as Data Cube.</p> <p>Only nitrogen monoxide, nitrogen dioxide, sulfur dioxide, ozone, PM2.5, PM10 and dust are regularly validated against in situ observations and hence considered as reliable.</p> <p>Time period covered: July 2018 to 2021.</p> <p>Temporal resolution: 1-hourly.</p> <p>Ensemble mean and surface data.</p>		
Type	Re-used		
License	<p>License to use Copernicus Products is available online (https://ads.atmosphere.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/cams-europe-air-quality-forecasts?tab=doc).</p>		
Description	<p>CAMS produces specific daily air quality analyses and forecasts for the European domain at a high spatial resolution (approximately 10km) based on an ensemble of nine air quality forecasting systems across Europe. A median ensemble is calculated from individual outputs. The analysis combines model data with <u>observations provided by the European Environment Agency (EEA)</u> into a complete and consistent dataset using various data assimilation techniques depending upon the air-quality forecasting system used.</p>		

Resource ID	RO1-GC0-SC3	Name	Bibliography on air quality before, during and after lockdown
Format	Bibliographic RO	Size	2223 KB
Source	https://w3id.org/ro-id/374d0d3a-4807-4925-be83-b9eea52356e3		
Type	Produced		

License	CC-BY
Description	Collection of scientific articles and other communications related to the impact of COVID-19 pandemic lockdown on air quality pollution.

Resource ID	RO2-GC0-SC3	Name	Jupyter Notebook analyzing the impact of lockdown on air quality
Format	Executable RO	Size	13.5 MB
Source	https://w3id.org/ro-id/53aa90bf-c593-4e6d-923f-d4711ac4b0e1		
Type	Produced		
License	MIT License		
Description	Tool to extract time series from CADS for all the different pollutants and for different locations.		

Resource ID	RO3-GC0-SC3	Name	Galaxy workflow and Galaxy histories for air quality analysis
Format	.ga, .cwl, json, html, svg	Size	21.6 KB
Source	https://w3id.org/ro-id/67edd16f-c3d8-4879-a3a5-2d223e7dce6d		
Type	Produced		
License	Apache Software License 2.0		
Description	Galaxy workflow and executed Galaxy histories for getting air quality indices from CADS on a given location		

Resource ID	RO4-GC0-SC3	Name	Jupyter notebook comparing CAMS and air quality measurements
Format	Executable RO	Size	7 MB
Source	https://w3id.org/ro-id/5f2e7ab8-8122-41b3-8d53-060e09855fa7		
Type	Produced		
License	MIT license		
Description	Compare CAMS analysis with available observations on specific locations.		

Resource ID	RO5-GC0-SC3	Name	Identification of sources of pollution events during lockdown
Format	Executable RO	Size	1 GB
Source	https://w3id.org/ro-id/d767e6c3-6cfd-4e68-a989-0b4cbe9236b5		
Type	Produced		
License	MIT License		
Description	Trajectory model (backwards) such as FLEXPART or HYSPLIT or LAGRANTO. Backward trajectories to find origin of events where high concentrations of pollutants have been found		

Resource ID	RO6-GC0-SC3	Name	Final report regarding the study of the impact of lockdown on air quality over Europe
Format	Bibliographic RO	Size	12 MB
Source	https://w3id.org/ro-id/66613047-4680-459d-8c60-509c349830d5		
Type	Produced		
License	CC-BY		
Description	This report assembles all the results obtained and discusses the findings.		

3.4. Scenario 4 “Analysis from satellite data – Environmental monitoring from space”

Water-quality monitoring requires observations at large spatial extensions, to assess both local and broad impacts, covering wide maritime areas at high spatial and temporal resolution. Natural environmental variability, diversity of ecosystems, and replication of data over sufficient spatial and temporal scales to provide an adequate and representative baseline, make monitoring activity a rather challenging task. Remote-sensing products represent the most suitable tool for this activity, due to their ability to provide quantitative and accessible information for scientists and managers at synoptic scale.

The following table summarizes the actions carried out during the scenario:

Action ID	Action description	Resources
1	Giorgio/Federico downloads the satellite products (Chl, TSM, Kd490) from ADAM Data Cube, allowing for subsetting in terms of spatial and temporal requirements	DS1-GC0-SC4
2	Federico creates a Dataset RO with the result of the query	RO1-GC0-SC4
3	Federico creates an Executable RO sharing the Jupyter notebook to replicate the query to ADAM platform	TO1-GC0-SC4 RO2-GC0-SC4
4	Giorgio creates a RO with the entire experiment linking all the previous resources (RO1-GC0-SC4 and RO2-GC0-SC4)	RO3-GC0-SC4

The following tables describe the resources re-used or produced during the scenario:

Resource ID	DS1-GC0-SC4	Name	NRT satellite products
Format	netCDF4	Size	5000 KB
Source	ADAM Platform		
Type	Re-used		
License	Data and products from Copernicus Sentinel-3 mission operated by EUMETSAT (hereinafter "Sentinel Data") made available in line with the Copernicus Sentinel data policy as defined in the Copernicus Programme and dedicated Commission Delegated Regulation (Copernicus Sentinel Data Policy (ESA/PB-EO(2013)30, rev 1; Regulation (EU) No 377/2014 and Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 1159/2013): https://eoportal.eumetsat.int/userMgmt/terms.faces		
Description	Near real-time L4 satellite products (Chl, TSM, Kd490)		

Resource ID	RO1-GC0-SC4	Name	“Satellite data on water clarity in the Venice Lagoon during the COVID19 lockdown”
Format	Dataset RO	Size	90.5 KB
Source	https://w3id.org/ro-id/894d3a33-8340-497d-beaf-5b9d85c9bfc7		
Type	Produced		
License	CC-BY		
Description	Research Object encapsulating the data resulting from the subsetting processing (DS1-GC0-SC4)		

Resource ID	TO1-GC0-SC4	Name	
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Format	Jupyter notebook	Size	227 KB
Source	https://notebooks.egi.eu/user/b285232f8bf5dc90b023ebc0c44ea0e0b883a51043a5c57b1d43b522a25548c9@egi.eu/lab/workspaces/auto-4/tree/Scenario%204%20%E2%80%9CAnalysis%20from%20satellite%20data%20%E2%80%93%20Environmental%20monitoring%20from%20space%E2%80%9D-Copy1.ipynb		
Type	Produced		
License	CC-BY		
Description	Procedure formalized in a Jupyter Notebook within the European Grid Infrastructure (EGI) and enabling the user to discover, subset and download satellite data stored in a Data Cube from the ADAM Platform		

Resource ID	RO2-GC0-SC4	Name	“Discover and subset satellite data from the ADAM Platform”
Format	Executable RO	Size	426 KB
Source	https://w3id.org/ro-id/34d648b3-0014-4a19-8469-40b9380ca4c3		
Type	Produced		
License	CC-BY		
Description	Executable RO for sharing and reuse the procedure TO1-GS0-SC4. RO2-GC0-SC4 ensures the replicability of the procedure and allows different users to retrieve the same dataset.		

Resource ID	RO3-GC0-SC4	Name	“Analysis from satellite data – Environmental monitoring from space”
Format	Basic RO	Size	523 KB
Source	https://w3id.org/ro-id/d0694eaf-a561-4c9f-9a70-17c296da2140		
Type	Produced		
License	CC-BY		
Description	The entire experiment is encapsulated in RO3-GC0-SC4 linking all the previous resources (RO1-GC0-SC4 and RO2-GC0-SC4) and potentially the scientific results (climatological means and anomalies of satellite variables) produced.		

3.5. Scenario 5 “Underwater Sound Pressure Level Analysis”

Assessing the impact of underwater environmental noise on the sensitive marine fauna is an important issue and it is specifically required by the Marine Strategy Framework Directive. Underwater noise is produced by natural and anthropogenic sources. In this scenario, underwater noise will be recorded by hydrophones close to the CNR “Acqua Alta” oceanographic tower during the lockdown and the Sound Pressure Level data collected will be analyzed to evaluate the potential effect of the Covid-19 restrictions on the underwater noise.

The following table summarizes the actions carried out during the scenario:

Action ID	Action description	Resources
1	Antonio downloads the wav raw data collected by hydrophone in the framework of the SOUNDSCAPE Project (https://www.italy-croatia.eu/web/soundscape) and uploads the wav nav files to the SNAPSHOT Project server (https://snapshot.d4science.org/)	DS1-GC0-SC5
3	Antonio uses the Audio Noise Processing App to process the wav data and retrieves the SPL data	TO1-GC0-SC5 DS2-GC0-SC5

4	Antonio integrates the app code for the processing in a Jupyter Notebook	TO2-GC0-SC5
5	Antonio develops a python script to post-process the SPL data and produce statistics and graphs about the underwater noise distribution over time for the different recording stations	TO3-GC0-SC5 DS3-GC0-SC5
6	Antonio integrates the python script for post-processing into Jupyter notebook for a dynamic processing of the data and presentation of the results	TO4-GC0-SC5
7	Antonio implements a Workflow RO to share the TO2-GC0-SC5 using the “rohuh” python library (Jupyter Notebook)	RO1-GC0-SC5 TO5-GC0-SC5
8	Antonio implements a Workflow RO to share the TO4-GC0-SC5 using TO5-GC0-SC5	RO2-GC0-SC5

The following tables describe the resources re-used or produced during the scenario:

Resource ID	DS1-GC0-SC5	Name	WAV Dataset
Format	Raw wav files (.wav)	Size	20 TB
Source	http://libeccio.bo.ismar.cnr.it:8080/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/317e007d-0813-4405-b2a1-b3650f255c6b		
Type	Produced		
License	Internal use only as agreed by the SOUNDSCAPE Project consortium		
Description	Recording of underwater noise. The raw wav files are collected through hydrophones, extracted and stored into a local server in Venice with a copy in IOF (Institute of Oceanography and fisheries, Split, Croatia)		

Resource ID	TO1-GC0-SC5	Name	Audio Noise Processing App
Format	Web app (URL)	Size	
Source	https://anp.soundscape.ve.ismar.cnr.it/		
Type	Produced		
License	The web application is proprietary and for internal use only. The code is open and available by Jupyter Notebook and shared as Workflow RO (see next tables)		
Description	The ANP app processes the raw wav files extracted from the hydrophone and produces SPL output files		

Resource ID	DS2-GC0-SC5	Name	SPL Dataset
Format	text file (.csv)	Size	70 GB
Source	http://libeccio.bo.ismar.cnr.it:8080/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/9b561f15-caab-4db9-aab4-84ca41c21cf7		
Type	Produced		
License	CC-BY		
Description	Results of the ANP app processing. The SPL dataset consists of .csv files downloaded from SPL files and obtained from ANP app.		

Resource ID	TO2-GC0-SC5	Name	SOUNDSCAPE underwater noise processing
Format	Jupyter Notebook	Size	
Source	https://notebooks.eqi.eu/user/da47d3640f619a02cb075c15d288fc09e053bf46b90d26ec335392acdfae866b@eqi.eu/doc/tree/datahub/Reliance/Soundscape/SoundscapeWAVProcessing.ipynb		

Type	Produced
License	CC-BY
Description	Jupyter SPL notebook with a script code to processes the raw wav files extracted from the hydrophone and produces SPL output files

Resource ID	TO3-GC0-SC5	Name	Python script
Format	Python code	Size	
Source	Python script produced in house, implemented with Jupyter SPL notebook and shared as Workflow RO (see RO1-GC0-SC5)		
Type	Produced		
License	CC-BY		
Description	Python script to post-process the SPL data and produce statistics and graphs		

Resource ID	DS3-GC0-SC5	Name	Graphs
Format	Images (.jpg)	Size	100 MB
Source	Results of the SPL data post-processing		
Type	Produced		
License	CC-BY		
Description	Underwater noise time series and statistics		

Resource ID	TO4-GC0-SC5	Name	SOUNDSCAPE underwater noise post-processing
Format	Jupyter Notebook	Size	
Source	https://notebooks.egi.eu/user/da47d3640f619a02cb075c15d288fc09e053bf46b90d26ec335392acdfae866b@egi.eu/doc/tree/datahub/Reliance/Soundscape/SoundscapePostProcessing.ipynb		
Type	Produced		
License	CC-BY		
Description	Python script to post-process the SPL data and produce statistics and graphs		

Resource ID	RO1-GC0-SC5	Name	SOUNDSCAPE WAV data to Sound Pressure Levels
Format	Workflow RO	Size	
Source	https://w3id.org/ro-id/6640422d-57ed-4814-b0d0-8eb4ee85f501		
Type	Produced		
License	CC-BY		
Description	Contains a Jupyter notebook (T02-GC0-SC5), that allows to calculate SPL values from wav data recorded by Develogic Sonovault Hydrophones.		

Resource ID	RO2-GC0-SC5	Name	SOUNDSCAPE Sound pressure Levels Post Processing
Format	Workflow RO	Size	
Source	https://w3id.org/ro-id/3f68f32e-1b6d-4689-acee-b797ba2c8429		
Type	Produced		
License	CC-BY		
Description	The Research Object shows how to post-process the SPL data		

Resource ID	TO5-GC0-SC5	Name	Creating Research Object
Format	Workflow in Jupyter Notebook	Size	

Source	Jupyter Notebook
Type	Produced
License	CC-BY
Description	Python script to create RO using "rohub" library

3.6. Scenario 6 "SNAPSHOT: Lockdown impacts on the Northern Adriatic Sea at selected site: AcquaAlta Platform Water quality"

This scenario investigates the impact of the lockdown event that happened in April 2020 on the northern Adriatic Sea marine ecosystem, specifically the water quality.

Intensive human activities impacted coastal ecosystems, through e.g., pollution and overfishing. The quality of sea water is crucial since it induces the quality of the marine ecosystem. Observations on water quality (physical and chemical) are a good indicator for the environmental conditions. Nutrient cycles for example have been altered in the past decades by human activities causing anthropogenic perturbations.

In this RO, we investigate the temporal evolution of the macronutrient, the example of nitrate with focus on the lockdown period during which the anthropogenic impacts have been reduced.

The following tables summarize the actions and steps:

Action ID	Action description	Resources
1	Malek downloads the dataset of the AcquaAlta Platform from external sources https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3516717	DS1-GC0-SC6
2	Malek processes the dataset of the AcquaAlta Platform in the northern Adriatic Sea using the Jupyter Notebook to investigate the impact of the lockdown and compare it with previous years (2009-2020) by checking the water quality using the following parameters: turbidity, inorganic nutrient to review the ecosystem productivity (it is a work in progress), in the present Jupyter notebook, we took the example of nitrate (NO ₃). Other Jupyter notebooks should follow.	TO1-GC0-SC6
3	Malek creates a workflow RO to share the script and aggregate all the materials and outputs	DS2-GC0-SC6
4	Malek creates a basic RO including metadata and related references to the dataset	RO1-GC0-SC6 TO1-GC0-SC6

The following tables describe the resources used and/or produced during Scenario n°6:

Resource ID	DS1-GC0-SC6	Name	AcquaAlta Platform north Adriatic Sea dataset
Format	Table (.xls, .csv)	Size	300-500 KB
Source	The present database contains observations for 21 parameters of abiotic data collected in the Northern Adriatic Sea region (Italy). It relies on a Comma Separated Values file. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3516717		
Type	Re-used		
License	Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY)		

Description	Dataset containing information (lat, long, depth, biogeochemical) of a site in the north Adriatic Sea.
-------------	--

Resource ID	TO1-GC0-SC6	Name	data visualization and prediction
Format	Jupyter notebook	Size	300-500 KB
Source	https://notebooks.egi.eu/user/f1451ae8e09f069810cff3a891928598acc5267d033f11bb40056da460482b3d@egi.eu/doc/tree/datahub/Reliance/Snapshot-PTF-ML/Snapshot%202021%20Lockdown%20impact%20using%20ML%20model-R.ipynb		
Type	Produced		
License	Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY)		
Description	the present notebook is used to predict the status of the water quality after the lockdown using machine learning		

Resource ID	DS2-GC0-SC6	Name	Workflow
Format	.png	Size	300-500 KB
Source	Workflow		
Type	Produced		
License	Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY)		
Description	workflow of RO including the adopted steps in Jupyter notebook and the creation of the final RO.		

Resource ID	<i>RO1-GC0-SC6</i>	Name	
Format	Executable RO	Size	300-500 KB
Source	https://w3id.org/ro-id/0869e396-3733-4aff-8fb2-94c8937b28aa		
Type	Produced		
License	Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY)		
Description	Snapshot 2021 study case: Lockdown impacts on the Northern Adriatic Sea at selected site: AcquaAlta Platform Water quality		

4. Requirements – RELIANCE services

*type: mandatory, desirable, optional

REQ01	RELIANCE webpage	source	type	status
a	The webpage should allow the user to access all the RELIANCE services (e.g. ROhub, Jupyter notebooks, ADAM)	all	mandatory	proposed
b	The webpage should allow the user to access the Galaxy platform	all	mandatory	proposed

REQ02	RELIANCE ROHub user interfaces	source	type	status
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a	If a user has several accounts (e.g. ORCID; EVER-EST or Google), ROhub should link the accounts or enable the moving/copy of ROs from an account to another	all	mandatory	done
b	Visualize in “My ROs” also the ROs of which the user is contributor or editor	all	desirable	approved
c	The button “Delete” in “My ROs” should ask “do you want to delete the RO?”	all	desirable	approved
d	<p>Four types/templates of ROs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bibliographic centric RO - Data centric RO (including Data Cube) - Executable) RO (including Jupyter) - No template is ‘basic’ RO (empty structure) <p>--- point 0 --- creation time</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - user can select one type/templates to automatically create initial structure <p>--- any time after creation ---</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - user can select/modify the associated RO type/template <p>---- checklist assessment ---</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - will automatically recommend checklist based on the associated RO type/template 	all	mandatory	proposed
e	Brief description of the meaning of the RO types	all	desirable	approved
f	Workflow ROs must not be linked to Taverna workflow but it should include any kind of workflows (code, script, WPS, model builder, etc.)	all	mandatory	is not linked
g	The “Template” option is not necessary because the type is already decided above.	all	desirable	approved

h	<p>Suggestion: once the type of RO is chosen, the template is taken automatically when a resource is added in “content” the field “ResourceType” is not necessary. This information is in the details of the resource that should be all mandatory</p>	all	desirable	rejected
i	<p>“Access mode” to be decided after the creation. The publication should be possible only when the quality requirements are satisfied</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Access mode will be possible to selected during creation time but not linked to quality 	all	desirable	rejected
l	<p>Quality checklist should represent the type of RO chosen at the creation, so the user doesn’t have to choose one</p>	all	mandatory	proposed
m	<p>Quality checklist should be limited to what is really important, limiting effort from the user. It should include:</p> <p>Common:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - title - mandatory - description - mandatory - creator - mandatory & automatic - credit - mandatory - publisher - mandatory & automatic - contributor - not mandatory - geolocation - not mandatory - sketch - mandatory - keywords - mandatory - subject (research area?) - mandatory - access level - mandatory - there is at least a resource in “content” - mandatory - there are all details for the resource - mandatory <p>Bibliographic-centric RO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - there is at least a resource in “biblio” - mandatory <p>Data-centric RO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - there is at least e resource in “raw data” - not mandatory - there is at least a resource in “data” - mandatory - there is at least e resource in “metadata” - mandatory 	all	mandatory	approved

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - there is at least a resource in “biblio” - not mandatory <p>Executable RO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - there is at least a resource in “input” - mandatory - there is at least a resource in “tool” - mandatory - there is at least a resource in “output” - mandatory - there is at least a resource in “biblio” - not mandatory 			
n	The mandatory items should be visible in the “overview tab”, not as annotation to be added manually by the user	all	desirable	approved
o	A “FAIRness” checklist (like what we get http://f-uji.net/). Our funding agencies asked researchers to be FAIR. If Rohub is an easy way to achieve FAIRness of research objects then it is very valuable	all	desirable	approved
p	Share RO in:		desirable	
p1	b2share	all	desirable	done
p2	Zenodo (ask about the DOI)	all	desirable	done
p3	Github	all	desirable	proposed

REQ03	DATA CUBE	source	Type	status
a	Discovery the following databases:			
a1	SeaDataNet Data Search Engine	CNR	desirable	ongoing
a2	Copernicus Marine Service	CNR	desirable	ongoing

a3	EUMETSAT	CNR	desirable	ongoing
a4	NOAA's National Centers for Environmental Information (NCEI)	CNR	desirable	proposed
a5	Ocean data (NASA)	CNR	desirable	proposed
a6	Coast colour	CNR	desirable	proposed
a7	Pangaea	CNR, INGV	desirable	proposed
a8	Snapshot VRE	CNR	desirable	proposed
a9	CNR-ISMAR resource catalogue	CNR	desirable	proposed
a10	EPOS Portal and the European Catalogue of Volcanoes (EUROVOLC)	INGV	desirable	proposed
a11	INGV data portal	INGV	desirable	proposed
a12	The CMIPv6 data portal.	UiO	desirable	proposed
a13	ADAM	Other	desirable	proposed
a14	OGC OpenSearch tools	Other	desirable	proposed
a15	STAC-based tools	Other	desirable	proposed
a16	Copernicus Climate Change Service	UiO	desirable	ongoing
a17	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service	UiO	desirable	ongoing
a18	Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project data repository (https://data.isimip.org/)	UiO	desirable	proposed
a19	Norwegian Infrastructure for Research Data Archive (https://archive.norstore.no/)	UiO	desirable	proposed
a20	Galaxy climate Reference datasets (https://galaxy-minio.uiogeo-apps.sigma2.no/)	UiO	desirable	proposed
b	filter the dataset by:			
b1	environmental variable		mandatory	proposed

b2	temporal extent		mandatory	done
b3	spatial extent		mandatory	done
b4	elevation (e.g. water depth)		desirable	proposed
d	download the data		mandatory	done
e	save my searches		mandatory	proposed

REQ04	Jupyter Hub and Notebook	source	type	status
a	Jupyter should allow the following languages:			
a1	R	CNR INGV	desirable	done
a2	Matlab	CNR INGV	desirable	done
a3	Python	CNR INGV	mandatory	done
a4	IDL	CNR INGV	desirable	proposed
b	Jupyter should have the following libraries:			
b1	numpy, scipy, rasterio, others TBD at the first tests	INGV	mandatory	proposed
b2	pangeo software stack (see https://github.com/pangeo-data/pangeo-docker-images/tree/master/pangeo-notebook)	UiO	desirable	proposed
c	Discovery the following databases:			
c1	SeaDataNet Data Search Engine	CNR	desirable	proposed
c2	Copernicus Marine Service	CNR	desirable	proposed

c3	NOAA's National Centers for Environmental Information (NCEI)	CNR	desirable	proposed
c4	Ocean data (NASA)	CNR	desirable	proposed
c5	Coast colour	CNR	desirable	proposed
c6	Pangaea	CNR, INGV	desirable	proposed
c7	Snapshot VRE	CNR	desirable	proposed
c8	CNR-ISMAR resource catalogue	CNR	desirable	proposed
c9	EPOS Portal and the European Catalogue of Volcanoes (EUROVOLC)	INGV	desirable	proposed
c10	INGV data portal	INGV	desirable	proposed
c11	The CMIPv6 data portal.	UiO	desirable	proposed
c12	ADAM	Other	desirable	proposed
c13	OGC OpenSearch tools	Other	desirable	proposed
c14	STAC-based tools	Other	desirable	proposed
c15	Copernicus Climate Change Service	UiO	desirable	proposed
c16	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service	UiO	desirable	proposed
c17	Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project data repository (https://data.isimip.org/)	UiO	desirable	proposed
c18	Norwegian Infrastructure for Research Data Archive (https://archive.norstore.no/)	UiO	desirable	proposed
c19	Galaxy climate Reference datasets (https://galaxy-minio.uiogeo-apps.sigma2.no/)	UiO	desirable	proposed
d	filter the dataset by:			
d1	environmental variable		desirable	proposed
d2	temporal extent		desirable	proposed
d3	spatial extent		desirable	proposed
d4	elevation (e.g. water depth)		desirable	proposed

e	visualize the data (graphic output and NetCDF)		desirable	proposed
f	process the data		desirable	proposed
g	download the data		desirable	proposed
h	operations with Research Objects (adding an explanation)		desirable	approved
h1	creation RO		desirable	approved
h2	describe RO		desirable	approved
h3	add resources (e.g. dataset, script, results)		desirable	approved
h4	set the “access control” parameters of the RO		desirable	approved
h5	Discover ROs in ROHub and use resources in them	INGV	mandatory	approved
h6	Export RO to Galaxy Climate history	UiO	desirable	approved
h7	Import RO from Galaxy climate history	UiO	desirable	approved
i	Other tools			
i1	Common Workflow Language (CWL)		mandatory	proposed

REQ05	Text Mining and Enrichment	source	Type	status
a	Extracting the influence network of a specific research work based on its authors’ impact in the community and the citations of the work		desirable	proposed - tbc
b	Automatically linking scientific publications with existing datasets relevant for a specific research		desirable	approved
c	Extract information from the following format of documents:		desirable	proposed
c1	Pdf		desirable	done
c2	Doc		desirable	done
c3	image (e.g. scanned document)		desirable	on hold

c4	excel/csv		desirable	rejected
c5	Html		desirable	proposed
d	enrichment of the RO with information extracted from annotations and resources		desirable	proposed
e	dashboard for extracted knowledge through text mining		desirable	proposed
f	plugin for automatically push the resources from text mining in the bibliographic RO		desirable	proposed
g	text mining to extract metadata from github, data cube....		desirable	proposed
h	recommandations (Spheres)		desirable	proposed

REQ06	Galaxy platform	source	type	status
a	Add a tool to export a User history as a RO to ROhub	UiO	desirable	proposed
b	Allow to import RO to Galaxy history	UiO	desirable	proposed
c	Add ADAM as a custom user resources (user old add their credentials in their Galaxy preferences).	UiO	desirable	proposed
d	Interoperability with Text mining services and Galaxy	UiO	desirable	proposed

REQ07	Other EOSC services and infrastructures	source	type	status
a1	Virtual machine: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 64 GB RAM 250 GB HD Linux 	CNR	mandatory	proposed
a2	Virtual machine: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 64 GB RAM 1TB storage Linux 	INGV	mandatory	proposed
a3	Virtual machine (Galaxy pulsar node) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 128 processors 92GB RAM 1TB storage Linux 	UiO	desirable	proposed

b1	Cloud storage 20 TB	CNR	desirable	proposed
b2	Cloud storage 25 TB	INGV	mandatory	proposed
b3	cloud storage 20 TB	UiO	desirable	proposed
c	Cloud computing space? JUPYTER?	CNR	desirable	proposed

5. Testing, demonstration and population

5.1. Research Objects Scenario 1

“Bibliography analysis on lockdown related papers within Earth science” aims at testing the RELIANCE text mining tools. The list of scientific papers, dealing with the COVID19 lockdown and Earth Sciences (DS1-GC0-SC1) and downloaded through Web of Science, (<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/basic-search>) is available in the RO (RO1-GC0-SC1) named “Earth Sciences papers about COVID19 lockdown”.

The screenshot shows the Reliance Research Object (RO) interface. At the top, there are navigation tabs: Overview, Content, Quality, Activity, Life cycle, Relations, and Impact. Below these are status indicators: PUBLIC, MANUAL, LIVE, and BASIC RESEARCH OBJECT. The title is "Bibliography analysis on lockdown related papers within Earth science" by Valentina Grande, created on 07 December 2021 (10:16). The description states that since the beginning of March 2020, many European and non-European countries went into an unprecedented lockdown, leading to a big number of papers analyzing the effect of the anthropause on the marine environment. This RO contains a list of scientific papers downloaded through Web of Science.

The interface includes several sections:

- CONTENT:** A list of papers (291Kb).
- ACTIVITY:** A record showing an annotation added on 15.12.2021 (12:53) by Valentina Grande, linked to the resource "List of papers".
- LIFE CYCLE CHART:** A chart showing the RO was created on 07.12.2021 (10:16) by Valentina Grande.
- AGENTS:** Lists the creator, Valentina Grande.
- QUALITY:** Shows a quality score of 0%.
- TOOLBOX:** Includes icons for download, RSS, settings, and other tools.
- SHARE:** Provides social media sharing options (link, email, Twitter, Facebook).
- CITE AS:** Provides the citation string: Grande, Valentina. "Bibliography analysis on lockdown related papers within Earth science." RO Hub. Dec 07, 2021. <https://w3id.org/ro-id/7f025f6e-9835-4af8-aa48-0152474eda37>.

At the bottom, there is a button to "Show All Annotations".

Figure 1. RO1-GC0-SC1. <https://w3id.org/ro-id/7f025f6e-9835-4af8-aa48-0152474eda37>.

For each paper it has been automatically created a Bibliographic RO (e.g. RO1-GC0-SC1), described by the Enrichment tool that automatically extracts all the metadata from the document.

Overview
Content
Quality
Activity
Life cycle
Relations
Impact

PUBLIC
MANUAL
LIVE
BIBLIOGRAPHY-CENTRIC RESEARCH OBJECT

ECOLOGY METEOROLOGY
Created: 10 December 2021 (10:59)

Changes in black carbon emissions over Europe due to COVID-19 lockdowns

Federica Foglini
Last modified: 10 December 2021 (10:59)

Description:

Following the emergence of the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) responsible for COVID-19 in December 2019 in Wuhan (China) and its spread to the rest of the world, the World Health Organization declared a global pandemic in March 2020. Without effective treatment in the initial pandemic phase, social distancing and mandatory quarantines were introduced as the only available preventative measure. In contrast to the detrimental societal impacts, air quality improved in all countries in which strict lockdowns were applied, due to lower pollutant emissions. Here we investigate...

[Show more >](#)

☆ 0.00 / 5

💬 0

❤️ 0

0 Downloads

0 Views

Hide more details

📁 Resources	1
📄 Annotations	10
📅 Events	12
🔗 Forks	0
📷 Snapshots	0
🗃️ Archives	0
📏 Size	5.02 KB

AGENTS

service-account-generation-...
 Creator

QUALITY

0%

TOOLBOX

📄
📡
⚙️
📁

SHARE

🔗
👥
🐦
📘

CITE AS

Foglini, Federica. "Changes in black carbon emissions over Europe due to COVID-19 lockdowns." ROHub. Dec 10, 2021. <https://w3id.org/ro-id/629b2be8-2457-44e9-bf8f-8aaba3fde6a8>.

CONTENT

📄 Changes in black carbon emissions over Europe due to COVID-19 lockdowns (1Kb)

ACTIVITY

View All ↗

📄 ANNOTATION
ADDED
→
RESOURCE
Changes in black carbon emissions...
 on 10.12.2021 (10:59) by service-account-generation-ser...

📄 ANNOTATION
ADDED
→
RESOURCE
Changes in black carbon emissions...
 on 10.12.2021 (10:59) by service-account-generation-ser...

📄 ANNOTATION
ADDED
→
RESOURCE
Changes in black carbon emissions...
 on 10.12.2021 (10:59) by service-account-generation-ser...

Figure 2. RO1-GC0-SC1.Example of Bibliographic RO.
<https://w3id.org/ro-id/629b2be8-2457-44e9-bf8f-8aaba3fde6a8>.

We will use the web user interface called *Collaboration Spheres* to explore the relationships between papers. The service will be tested for the next release of this document.

5.2. Research Objects Scenario 2

“Marine Monitoring during the Anthropause” - The [research object](#) shares the dataset and analysis gathered from the questionnaire carrying the same name, i.e. “Marine Monitoring during the Anthropause” (https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSe9yaL-IV4bLW41sc482YxxV-TKYP6WtLK7iTVehgWOrtTqrg/viewform?usp=sf_link).

The research object enlightens the process that we are undertaking to understand the answers of the scientific community to the anthropogenic de-impact that took place during the pandemic.

The measures taken to prevent the spread of COVID19 influenced our way of life and our way of making science. It also gave to the scientific community the biggest experimental pool ever recorded to study the impact on the natural environment of reduced human activities. Studies reported wildfires diminishing, fisheries pausing, transport and commerce shrinking; people witnessed more wildlife sightings close to inhabited areas. We built an inventory of all existing monitoring efforts of

the marine environment that have been put in place in the seas and oceans, to assess the impact (or de-impact) of the Covid-19 - related lockdowns.

Among the resources included in the Research Object there are:

- [link to the questionnaire](#)
- [link to the presentation of the first outcome of the questionnaire](#)
- an image showing the category of the data gathered during the pandemic
- an image showing the parameters measured during the pandemic

The screenshot shows the ROHub interface for a Research Object titled "Marine Monitoring during the Anthropause" by Simona Aracri. The interface includes a navigation bar with tabs for Overview, Content, Quality, Activity, Life cycle, Relations, and Impact. The "Overview" tab is active. Below the navigation bar, there are status indicators: PRIVATE, MANUAL, LIVE, and BASIC RESEARCH OBJECT. The object is categorized under APPLIED SCIENCES and was created on 17 November 2021 (15:41). The title "Marine Monitoring during the Anthropause" is prominently displayed, followed by the creator's name, Simona Aracri, and the last modified date, 20 December 2021 (12:03). A description follows, detailing the pandemic's impact on the scientific community and the project's goal to assess the impact of Covid-19 related lockdowns on the marine environment. A "Collapse description" link is provided. On the right side, there are statistics for Downloads (0) and Views (0), along with a "Hide more details" link. Below this, a table lists various resources and their counts: Resources (4), Annotations (15), Events (20), Forks (0), Snapshots (0), Archives (0), and Size (320.81 KB). At the bottom right, the "AGENTS" section shows Simona Aracri as the Creator.

Figure 3. RO1-GC0-SC2: Marine Monitoring during the Anthropause - Research Object as seen in the ROHub interface (<https://w3id.org/ro-id/49f52ad4-bf2c-4f50-9242-a26962d5a7a2>).

Figure 4. Parameters measured during the pandemic.

Figure 5. Graph showing under which category marine data collected during the pandemic fall under.

5.3. Research Objects Scenario 3

In this case study we have created 5 different ROs related to the investigation of the lockdown effect on air quality between January 2019 to May 2021. The corresponding Jupyter Notebooks as well as the Galaxy histories and Galaxy workflow are made openly available for everyone to see exactly what analysis has been done, which data source was used, how we proceeded to prepare the data and derive relevant metrics, how we defined the plots (including the min/max thresholds we have set to highlight patterns of interest) and how we came to the conclusions.

The first RO (RO1-GC0-SC3) is a bibliographic RO (<https://w3id.org/ro-id/374d0d3a-4807-4925-be83-b9eea52356e3>) containing a collection of scientific papers and other information related to the analysis of air quality before, during and after the lockdown. Most of the resources are Web URLs but some articles have also been added as pdf. The content of this RO is relevant for all the other ROs on the impact of lockdown on air quality that we have generated. This RO is live and new content can be added when a new scientific paper of interest is read by researchers.

The second RO (RO1-GC0-SC3) is an executable RO containing a Jupyter Notebook analyzing the impact of lockdown on air quality (<https://w3id.org/ro-id/53aa90bf-c593-4e6d-923f-d4711ac4b0e1>) using model data from the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service. The data we have used was extracted from the Data Cube (DS1-GC0-SC3) that greatly facilitated the process. Data access and possibility to subset data on a very fine grain (using complex geometry provided as json file) were appreciated by researchers. More than 14 results (figures, new dataset products such as time series) were generated and can be reused by anyone.

Overview | Content | Quality | Activity | Life cycle | Relations | Impact

PUBLIC MANUAL LIVE EXECUTABLE RESEARCH OBJECT

APPLIED SCIENCES METEOROLOGY

Created: 19 December 2021 (22:18)

Impact of the Covid-19 Lockdown on Air quality over Europe

Anne Fouilloux

Last modified: 19 December 2021 (23:11)

Description:

The COVID-19 pandemic has led to significant reductions in economic activity, especially during lockdowns. Several studies has shown that the concentration of nitrogen dioxide and particulate matter levels have reduced during lockdown events. Reductions in transportation sector emissions are most likely largely responsible for the NO2 anomalies. In this study, we analyze the impact of lockdown events on the air quality using data from Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service over Europe and at selected locations.

Sketch:

☆ 0.00 / 5 | 0 | 0

0 Downloads	0 Views
Hide more details	
Resources	17
Annotations	47
Events	75
Forks	0
Snapshots	0
Archives	0
Size	21915.11 KB

AGENTS
 Anne Fouilloux
 Creator

QUALITY 0%

TOOLBOX

Click to copy RO-link

CITE AS
 Fouilloux, Anne. "Impact of the Covid-19 Lockdown on Air quality over Europe." ROHub. Dec 19, 2021. <https://w3id.org/ro-id/53aa90bf-c593-4e6d-923f-d4711ac4b0e1>.

Error has occurred with loadROLicense

CONTENT

- NO2 mean over March-June for 2019, 2020 and 2021 (736Kb)
- Timeseries of PM2.5 at 12 different locations (1450Kb)
- Total averaged NO2 at 12 differents locations (25Kb)
- Maximum O3 for 2019, 2020 and 2021 over March-June (834Kb)
- tools
 - Impact of the lockdown on air quality
 - Air quality over Europe during lockdown (13120Kb)

Figure 6. RO1-GC0-SC3: Air quality Monitoring over the COVID-19 pandemic - Research Object as seen in the ROHub interface <https://w3id.org/ro-id/53aa90bf-c593-4e6d-923f-d4711ac4b0e1>.

The third RO (RO3-GC0-SC3) collates all the Galaxy histories generated running the Galaxy workflow "Investigation of lockdown effect on air quality between January 2019 to May 2021". The Galaxy workflow itself is published on [WorkflowHub](https://www.workflowhub.eu/), a registry for describing, sharing and publishing scientific computational workflows which provides the possibility to execute it directly on the Galaxy Europe instance (<https://usegalaxy.eu/>) by the click of a button (resource available to everyone after registration). The analysis performed here focuses on specific geographical areas and time periods where citizens had experienced significant degradation of air quality during the lockdown. Having a Galaxy workflow makes it easier for citizens to perform a similar analysis over different locations and time ranges because Galaxy provides a Graphical User Interface accessible without programming experience: users can easily upload data, run complex tools and workflows, and visualize results.

Investigation of lockdown effect on air quality between January 2019 to May 2021. Version 1

Workflow Type: Galaxy
 Stable

This workflow extracts 5 different time periods e.g. January- June 2019, 2020 and 2021, July-December 2019 and 2020 over a single selected location. Then statistics (mean, minimum, maximum) are computed. The final products are maximum, minimum and mean.

SEEK ID: <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/251?version=1>
 DOI: [10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.251.1](https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.251.1)

Steps

ID	Name	Description
----	------	-------------

Figure 7. RO3-GC0-SC3: Galaxy workflow “Investigation of lockdown effect on air quality between January 2019 to May 2021” on WorkflowHub.eu ([10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.251.1](https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.251.1)).

The DOI of the Galaxy workflow (<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.251.1>) is then added as an external resource of RO3-GC0-SC3. The RO is available on ROHub at <https://w3id.org/ro-id/67edd16f-c3d8-4879-a3a5-2d223e7dce6d> as an executable RO.

RO4-GC0-SC3 is an executable RO containing a Jupyter notebook related to the comparison between CAMS and observations. The research object is available at <https://w3id.org/ro-id/5f2e7ab8-8122-41b3-8d53-060e09855fa7> and is a live RO. Observations are from EBAS, a database with atmospheric measurement data operated by NILU (Norwegian Institute for Air Research) and CAMS time series are RO1-GC0-SC3.

Creators and Submitter

Creators
Not specified

Submitter
 Anne Fouilloux

Citation

Fouilloux, A. (2021). *Investigation of lockdown effect on air quality between January 2019 to May 2021*. WorkflowHub. <https://doi.org/10.48546/WORKFLOWHUB.W>

American Psychological Association 7th

License
Apache Software License 2.0

Overview
Content
Quality
Activity
Life cycle
Relations
Impact

PUBLIC
MANUAL
LIVE
EXECUTABLE RESEARCH OBJECT

Created: 20 December 2021 (12:28)

Jupyter notebook comparing CAMS and air quality measurements

Anne Fouilloux
Last modified: 20 December 2021 (18:58)

Description:
Compare CAMS analysis with available observations on specific locations.
Sketch:

NO2 CAMS timeseries over March-June averaged over 3 years 2019, 2020 and 2021

CONTENT

- 📄 PM2.5 EBAS Data for Hurdal (NO0056R) (6Kb)
- 📄 CAMS O3 March-June 2019, 2020, 2021 (282Kb)
- 📄 CAMS NO2 March-June 1019, 2020, 2021 (283Kb)
- 📄 CAMS PM2.5 March-June 2019, 2020, 2021 (282Kb)
- 📄 output
- 📄 NO2 Timeseries 2019, 2020 and 2021 over Madrid (100Kb)
- 📄 CAMS timeseries (793Kb)

☆ 0.00 / 5 💬 0 ❤️ 0

0
Downloads

0
Views

Hide more details

📁 Resources	9
📄 Annotations	33
📅 Events	46
🔗 Forks	0
📷 Snapshots	0
📁 Archives	0
📏 Size	1001.63 KB

AGENTS

Anne Fouilloux

Creator

QUALITY 0%

TOOLBOX

📄
📡
⚙️
📁
📏

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🔗
👥
🐦
📘

CITE AS

Fouilloux, Anne. "Jupyter notebook comparing CAMS and air quality measurements." ROHub. Dec 20, 2021. <https://w3id.org/ro-id/5f2e7ab8-8122-41b3-8d53-060e09855fa7>.

Figure 8. RO4-GC0-SC3: Comparison of air quality measurements and CAMS analysis over the COVID-19 pandemic - Research Object as seen in the ROHub interface <https://w3id.org/ro-id/5f2e7ab8-8122-41b3-8d53-060e09855fa7>

In RO5-GC0-SC3 (<https://w3id.org/ro-id/d767e6c3-6cfd-4e68-a989-0b4cbe9236b5>), we aimed at identifying the sources of pollution events during lockdown using the HYSPLIT model which simulates the dispersion and trajectory of substances transported and dispersed through our atmosphere, over local to global scales.

Finally, with RO6-GC0-SC3 (<https://w3id.org/ro-id/66613047-4680-459d-8c60-509c349830d5>), we started to put together some of the results obtained on the air quality changes during the lockdown and highlight the main findings. This RO is still under construction and would be enriched by researchers as the work progresses.

5.4. Research Objects Scenario 4

“Analysis from satellite data – Environmental monitoring from space” shows how to discover, subset and download satellite data stored in a Data Cube from the ADAM Platform. The procedure is formalized in a Jupyter Notebook within the European Grid Infrastructure (EGI).

The data resulting from the subsetting processing (DS1-GC0-SC4) are encapsulated in the RO “Satellite data on water clarity in the Venice Lagoon during the COVID 19 lockdown” (RO1-GC0-SC4) allowing the scientist to obtain a persistent identifier (DOI).

Overview Content Quality Activity Life cycle Relations Impact

PUBLIC MANUAL LIVE DATA-CENTRIC RESEARCH OBJECT

APPLIED SCIENCES EARTH SCIENCES OPTICS PHYSICAL SCIENCES Created: 07 December 2021 (16:44)

Satellite data on water clarity in the Venice Lagoon during the COVID 19 lockdown

Giorgio Castellan

Last modified: 14 December 2021 (10:09)

Description:

Satellite Data on Chlorophyll-a and diffuse attenuation coefficient at 490 nm (Kd490) for the Venice Lagoon

Sketch:

☆ 0.00 / 5 1 ❤️ 0

0 Downloads 1 Views
[Hide more details](#)

📁 Resources	3
📄 Annotations	15
📅 Events	24
🔗 Forks	0
📷 Snapshots	0
📁 Archives	0
📦 Size	163.63 KB

AGENTS
 Giorgio Castellan
 Creator

QUALITY 0%

TOOLBOX

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CITE AS
 Castellan, Giorgio. "Satellite data on water clarity in the Venice Lagoon during the COVID 19 lockdown." ROHub. Dec 07, 2021. <https://w3id.org/ro-id/894d3a33-8340-497d-beaf-5b9d85c9bfc7>.

Figure 9. RO1-GC0-SC4: <https://w3id.org/ro-id/894d3a33-8340-497d-beaf-5b9d85c9bfc7>.

The Jupyter Notebook (TO1-GC0-SC4) is available through the RO “Discover and subset satellite data from the ADAM Platform” (RO2-GC0-SC4) and ensures the replicability of the procedure, allowing different users to retrieve the same dataset.

Overview | Content | Quality | Activity | Life cycle | Relations | Impact

PUBLIC | MANUAL | LIVE | EXECUTABLE RESEARCH OBJECT

EARTH SCIENCES

Created: 14 December 2021 (10:50)

Discover and subset satellite data from the ADAM Platform

Giorgio Castellani

Last modified: 14 December 2021 (11:32)

Description:

This Research Object demonstrate how to discover, subset and download satellite data stored in a Data Cube from the ADAM Platform

Sketch:

☆ 0.00 / 5 | 0 | 0

0	1
Downloads	Views
Hide more details	
Resources	3
Annotations	14
Events	25
Forks	0
Snapshots	0
Archives	0
Size	80.61 KB

AGENTS
Giorgio Castellani
Creator

QUALITY 0%

TOOLBOX
[Download] [Share] [Settings] [Layers] [Edit]

SHARE
[Link] [Reddit] [Twitter] [Facebook]

CITE AS
Castellani, Giorgio. "Discover and subset satellite data from the ADAM Platform." ROHub. Dec 14, 2021. <https://w3id.org/ro-id/34d648b3-0014-4a19-8469-40b9380ca4c3>.

CONTENT

- biblio
- input
 - Satellite data on water clarity in the Venice Lagoon during the COVID 19 lockdown
- output
- tool
 - Retrieve and visualize satellite data on Chl-a and Kd490 extracted from ADAM Platform (142Kb)
 - Schematic illustration of ADAM Platform Data Cube exploration and use (314Kb)

Figure 10. RO2-GC0-SC4: <https://w3id.org/ro-id/34d648b3-0014-4a19-8469-40b9380ca4c3>.

The entire experiment is encapsulated in the third RO named "Analysis from satellite data – Environmental monitoring from space" (RO3-GC0-SC4) linking all the previous resources (RO1-GC0-SC4 and RO2-GC0-SC4) and the scientific results (climatological means and anomalies of satellite variables).

Overview | Content | Quality | Activity | Life cycle | Relations | Impact

PUBLIC MANUAL LIVE BASIC RESEARCH OBJECT

EARTH SCIENCES

Created: 14 December 2021 (11:41)

Analysis from satellite data – Environmental monitoring from space

Giorgio Castellan

Last modified: 14 December 2021 (15:38)

Description:

Collection and analysis of satellite data to monitor the effects of COVID-19 lockdown on water clarity in the north Adriatic Sea

Sketch:

☆ 0.00 / 5 | 0 | 0

0 Downloads | 1 Views
Hide more details

Resources	5
Annotations	17
Events	28
Forks	0
Snapshots	0
Archives	0
Size	131.39 KB

AGENTS
Giorgio Castellan
Creator

QUALITY 0%

TOOLBOX

SHARE

CITE AS
Castellan, Giorgio. "Analysis from satellite data – Environmental monitoring from space." ROHub. Dec 14, 2021. <https://w3id.org/ro-id/d0694eaf-a561-4c9f-9a70-17c296da2140>.

CONTENT

- Method
 - Discover and subset satellite data from the ADAM Platform
- Results
 - Diffuse attenuation coefficient at 490 nm (Kd490) in 2018 in the north Adriatic Sea (67Kb)
 - Diffuse attenuation coefficient at 490 nm (Kd490) in 2018 in the north Adriatic Sea (69Kb)
- Satellite_data
 - Satellite data on water clarity in the Venice Lagoon during the COVID-19 lockdown

Figure 11. RO3-GC0-SC4: <https://w3id.org/ro-id/d0694eaf-a561-4c9f-9a70-17c296da2140>.

5.5. Research Objects Scenario 5

“Underwater Sound Pressure Level Analysis” shows: 1) how to elaborate wav data collected within the soundscape Project SOUNDSCAPE (<https://www.italy-croatia.eu/web/soundscape>) in order to produce Sound Pressure Levels (SPL) data; 2) how to post process SPL data to obtain some statistics and graphs.

Two ROs were developed to illustrate these tasks using the python library named “rohub” and developed in the framework of the Reliance Project with the aim to let users create and populate ROs using python code rather than using the online procedure. So, a Jupyter Notebook (TO5-GC0-SC5) was developed as a template to create RO and it was used to produce RO1-GC0-SC5 and RO2-GC0-SC5.

Creating Research Object

```
[1]: import rohuh
import inspect

log in

[30]: rohuh.login(username='antonio.petrizzo@ve.ismar.cnr.it', password='xxxxxxx')

Logged successfully as antonio.petrizzo@ve.ismar.cnr.it.

Create RO

[ ]: ro_title="Soundscape Sound Pressure Levels Post Processing"
ro_research_areas=["Earth sciences"]
ro_description="This RO shows more of 1 year of SPL Sound Pressure Levels (march 2020 - june 2021) obtained within the Soundscape Project - SOUNDSCAPES IN THE NORTH ADRIATIC SEA AND
ro_ros_type="Workflow-centric Research Object"
ro_access = "PUBLIC"

[ ]: ro = rohuh.ros_create(title=ro_title, research_areas=ro_research_areas,access_mode = ro_access,ros_type=ro_ros_type,
description=ro_description)

Adding resources

Jupyter notebook

[ ]: #external_resources (Link)
res_file_path="https://notebooks.egi.eu/user/da47d3640f619a02cb075c15d288fc09e053bf46b90d26ec335392acdfae066b@egi.eu/files/datahub/Reliance/Soundscape/SoundscapePostProcessing.ipynb"
res_res_type="Jupyter Notebook"
res_title="Sound Pressure Levels Processing"
res_description="This Notebook elaborates SPL data obtained by processing wav files recorded with Develogic SonoVault hydrophone."
rohuh.ros_add_external_resource(identi, res_type=res_res_type,input_url=res_file_path, title=res_title, description=res_description)

sketch
```

Figure 12. T05-GC0-SC5. Template Jupyter Notebook to create RO in the ROHub portal (<https://reliance.rohub.org/>).

The first RO (RO1-GC0-SC5) named "Soundscape WAV data to Sound Pressure Levels" is available at <https://w3id.org/ro-id/6640422d-57ed-4814-b0d0-8eb4ee85f501>. It contains a Jupyter notebook (T02-GC0-SC5), that allows to calculate SPL values from wav data recorded by Develogic Sonovault Hydrophones.

PUBLIC MANUAL LIVE WORKFLOW-CENTRIC RESEARCH OBJECT

EARTH SCIENCES

Created: 09 December 2021 (16:16)

Soundscape WAV data to Sound Pressure Levels

Antonio Petrizzo

Last modified: 14 December 2021 (13:49)

Description:

It allows to calculate Sound Pressure Levels from wav files. This is the code used within the Soundscape Project - SOUNDSCAPES IN THE NORTH ADRIATIC SEA AND THEIR IMPACT ON MARINE BIOLOGICAL RESOURCES (<https://www.italy-croatia.eu/web/soundscape>). It works with wav files recorded by Develogic SonoVault Hydrophones

Sketch:

LOCATION:

Area 1

CONTENT

- Wav File example
- metadata
 - Maps of the stations (1196Kb)
 - RO to process SPL data
- notebook
 - Wav to SPL processing
- results
 - SPL output file example (66Kb)

ACTIVITY [View All](#)

☆ 0.00 / 5 0 0

0	1
Downloads	Views
Hide more details	
Resources	8
Annotations	30
Events	65
Forks	0
Snapshots	0
Archives	0
Size	3069.21 KB

AGENTS

Antonio Petrizzo
Creator

QUALITY 0%

TOOLBOX

Download, RSS, Settings, Share, Edit

SHARE

Link, Print, Twitter, Facebook

CITE AS

Petrizzo, Antonio. "Soundscape WAV data to Sound Pressure Levels." ROHub. Dec 09, 2021. <https://w3id.org/ro-id/6640422d-57ed-4814-b0d0-8eb4ee85f501>.

Figure 13. RO1-GC0-SC5: <https://w3id.org/ro-id/6640422d-57ed-4814-b0d0-8eb4ee85f501>.

The second RO (RO2-GC0-SC5) named "Soundscape Sound Pressure Levels Post Processing" shows how to post-process the SPL data (<https://w3id.org/ro-id/3f68f32e-1b6d-4689-acee-b797ba2c8429>). The code to perform this elaboration is encapsulated in a Jupyter Notebook (TO2-GC0-SC5).

at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3516717>. All the necessary tasks are summarized in the flowchart RO2-GC0-SC6 below. These different steps were necessary to generate the RO.

Figure 15: DS2-GC0-SC6 Workflow of the RO with some outputs.

The RO include all steps described in the workflow, by making available the tool to process, visualize, compare the data. The tool is developed and built using R as a programming language under the Jupyter environment of EGI <https://notebooks.egi.eu/>. This is a reusable code that can be applied to any data having the same format (.csv) as the dataset used in the current RO. The RO contains resources about the dataset with detailed description, in this section, we present some of the preliminary outputs. Here we present the Jupyter notebook TO1-GC0-SC6 as a tool to plot and explore, visualize time series, and extract a data subset. It also includes some statistical operations: we averaged and extracted observations from the upper layer in the first 2m to visualize the Nitrate times series. And then to identify the difference between the years 2020 and the previous years. To do so, we used the random Forest known as a supervised machine learning g algorithm, taking into consideration all the variables to predict the trend of nitrate in 2020. Statistical control of the model is also available to review its reliability. The percentage of change is also computed to quantify this difference between years and compared to the entire period (2009-2019) as highlighted in the plots aggregated in the RO (folder outputs) This RO is under construction, it is a work in progress, and is subjected to further modifications and updates.

Overview Content Quality Activity Life cycle Relations Impact

PUBLIC **MANUAL** **LIVE** **BASIC RESEARCH OBJECT**

BIOCHEMISTRY EARTH SCIENCES OCEANOGRAPHY Created: 29 November 2021 (15:45)

Snapshot 2021 study case: Lockdown impacts on the Northern Adriatic Sea at selected site: AcquaAlta Platform Water quality

Malek Belgacem
Last modified: 15 December 2021 (16:16)

Description:
This is a case study of snapshot project <http://snapshot.cnr.it/> to investigate the lockdown impact on the water quality at a selected site in the northern Adriatic Sea, precisely in Northern Adriatic Sea, the case of the Gulf of Venice using Machine Learning model.

LOCATION:

CONTENT

- A long-term (1965–2015) ecological marine database from the LTER-Italy Northern Adriatic Sea site: plankton and oceanographic observations
- LTER Northern Adriatic Sea (Italy) marine data
- RO workflow (435Kb)

0.00 / 5 ☆ 0 0

0 Downloads 0 Views
[Hide more details](#)

Resources	3
Annotations	14
Events	23
Forks	0
Snapshots	0
Archives	0
Size	407.41 KB

AGENTS
Malek Belgacem
Creator

QUALITY 0%

TOOLBOX

SHARE

Figure 16. RO1-GC0-SC6: <https://w3id.org/ro-id/0869e396-3733-4aff-8fb2-94c8937b28aa>

All the resources are aggregated in the RO (sketch below), from the dataset, the Jupyter tool, metadata, study area to the outputs.

information contributors Tags gallery Resources locations Funding metadata

Basic information
Authors & contributors
Tags
Sketches gallery
Resources

Home

<input type="checkbox"/> Name	Details	Created	Creator
<input type="checkbox"/> Dataset	1 Entries	22 December 2021 (13:09)	Malek Belgacem
<input type="checkbox"/> Jupyter_tool	1 Entries	22 December 2021 (13:13)	Malek Belgacem
<input type="checkbox"/> Output	4 Entries	22 December 2021 (15:05)	Malek Belgacem
<input type="checkbox"/> A long-term (1965–2015) ecological marine database from the LTER-Italy Northern Adriatic Sea site: plankton and oceanographic observations		15 December 2021 (16:06)	Malek Belgacem

Figure 17. How to cite the research object: Belgacem, Malek. "Snapshot 2021 study case: Lockdown impacts on the Northern Adriatic Sea at selected site: AcquaAlta Platform Water quality." ROHub. Nov 29, 2021. <https://w3id.org/ro-id/0869e396-3733-4aff-8fb2-94c8937b28aa>.

6. Conclusions

This document reports the main steps needed to demonstrate the efficacy of the RELIANCE services within the EOSC context through real-life multidisciplinary user case studies provided by different scientific communities.

Firstly, the document reports 6 different scientific scenarios drafted so far in relation to the multidisciplinary case study on the 2020 lockdown involving the marine and atmospheric communities, respectively represented by CNR and University of OSLO.

The scenarios include the actions performed by scientists and all resources needed with a detailed description including format, source, type and license. The scenarios represent the basis for the definition of the technical requirements for the implementation of the RELIANCE services within the EOSC context. The requirements considered mandatory from the scientific communities and deemed fundamental for running the RELIANCE services including RO, Data Cube and Text mining were satisfied and marked as done, while most of the approved desirable requirements are still under implementation. Some requirements were rejected because they were considered by the RELIANCE technical partners not feasible. The requirement table represents a reference for the technical partners for the entire life span of the project and can be modified and integrated successively.

Finally, the document shows the testing phase represented by the creation and population of ROs for the different scenarios that imply the usage of the EGI Jupyter notebook, the ADAM platform and the ROhub services and APIs. The text mining services will be tested for the next WP7 deliverable due at M24. The testing phase was successful and fully demonstrated the potential of the RELIANCE services integrated into the EOSC context to foster multidisciplinary and to face different aspects of COVID19 lockdown event.

The next step will be to effectively link the different ROs to obtain a comprehensive scenario of the 2020 lockdown including both the marine and atmospheric studies and non-Earth Science community that will be involved as early adopters in the next months of the project.